

DETERMINING FACTORS FOR CHINA UNDERGRADUATE TO STUDY IN MALAYSIAN HIGHER LEARNING INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to determine the factors for china undergraduate to study in Malaysia higher learning institutions, whereby understanding the factors which influence the student's decision to study in Malaysia is very much needed. "Push-Pull" theory has been widely applied in the field of education, including the phenomenon of studying abroad. The push-pull factor theory has become a widely accepted analytical framework to explain the reasons for international students' mobility. The target population of this study is all the third-year high school students, who are in the urban area of four third-tier cities in Jiangxi province of China. In this study, the unlimited probability sampling design or simple random sampling is utilized finally. This research has contributed to the theoretical implications. Notably, this study improves the current written literature on influential factors towards intention of student enrolment in HEI. The factors being examined are student belief, social influence and brand equity. Moreover, the finding indicates that all the independent variables have a significant relationship towards foreign student enrolment. Therefore, the finding from this study can help researchers to have a clear insight and greater understanding of foreign students' enrolment of HEI in Malaysia in future by referring this research.

Keywords: determining factors, China undergraduate, study in Malaysian higher learning institutions

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1. Introduction

The choices available for students to study abroad have become a popular research field in higher education since student mobility has become a movement in recent decades. The number of students studying abroad is estimated at 8 million (Altbach, 2016), mainly comprises of undergraduate students and with overall expenses for undergraduate education are estimated at approximately 71,000 U.S. dollars (Hongkong and Shanghai Banking Corporation [HSBC], 2017), the total market value of international higher education can be calculated to be around 568 billion dollars by 2025. In this regard, students studying abroad can be regarded as an essential part of student mobility in the international higher education market (Hemsley-Brown & Oplatka, 2016). Therefore, an examination of factors associated with how international students choose colleges is crucial. The aim of this study is to investigate factors leading China students to choose higher education in Malaysia. In this regard, this research is a case study focusing on the factors affecting the factors of China students choosing to study in Malaysia. This study contributes to understanding international students' choices of colleges in developing countries. However, this study will focus on China students choosing Malaysia as their preferred higher learning destination due to the similar culture, recognition and affordability.

There are many scholars revealed either on general student's enrolment and examines more on other countries foreign student's enrolment. For instance, they showed that their key finding is comparative analysis toward Private versus Public Higher Education Institution for general students (Wilkinson & Yussof, 2005). This study aims to provide a valuable insight in the aspect of general students' enrolment in HEI. Whereas another study "Internationalization of Tertiary Education Services in Singapore" by Toh (2012) which study the foreign student enrolls in Singapore; "The Geography of Foreign Students in U.S. Higher Education: Origins and Destinations" establish by Ruiz (2014) that study about the foreign student enrolls in United Kingdom; Understanding India: "The future of higher education and opportunities for international cooperation" by Everitt (2014) that regards to foreign student in India; Immigration Facts on Foreign Students by Ruiz (2010) study of foreign students in several countries such as Australia, United Kingdom, United State, Italy and etc. The purpose of these studies was to investigate the characteristics of foreign students to pursue their studies in private universities or public universities in overseas. This study examines factors influencing Malaysian students' intention to study at a higher educational institution (Wagner & Fard, 2009). However, the uniqueness of this study is focus on the foreign students' enrolment in Malaysian Higher Learning Institution.

2. Literature Review

The rapid economic development has created a large number of middle-income families. It is estimated that by 2020, the urban middle-income families will reach 50%. These

families have a certain ability to pay, and there is an urgent need for quality HE. Under such circumstances, studying abroad is the best choice (Kuang & Qi, 2016). Family environment is an important factor and a direct factor affecting their children to study abroad. The family environment forms great influence in the decision making, but the educational background of the family members and the economic conditions of the family are undoubtedly one of the most basic and most important factors. This will not only affect individual's decision to study abroad at their own expense, but also affects the intention of studying abroad (Liu, 2016). Family income has a significant impact on the decision-making behavior of high school students studying abroad at their own expense (Wang, 2014). The cost of studying abroad is an important aspect for many families to choose to study abroad. The number of household income will affect the country and school to a certain extent, and the children of low-income families are less likely to go abroad at their own expense (Liu, 2015). There is a positive correlation between students' intention to study abroad and the income of their families, that is, the higher the income of the students' families, the more likely the students to study abroad, the higher the income level of the family and the better conditions for the students to study abroad (Sun, 2017). The education level of father and mother has a significant impact on the decision-making behavior of high school students studying abroad at their own expense (Wang, 2014). With the increasing education level of parents, the possibility of their children going abroad to study is greater (Liu, 2015). It is the most significant difference when parents' education level is above college or below. If parents' education level is above college, students are more inclined to study abroad (Sun, 2017). Children from the family background of intellectuals and professionals are the most intention to study abroad, followed by civil servants' family and business families, ordinary workers and families, and the farmers' family origin students' desire is the weakest (Wang, 2014). The type of parents' occupation has a certain impact on students' intention to go abroad for cross-border HE (Sun, 2017).

Zhan (2017) found that the annual family income means the ability to pay to some extent. A family's annual income which is above RMB200,000, has a higher impact in the decision-making on studying abroad. Among families with annual incomes of more than RMB300,000, nearly half of them have made decisions to study abroad. For families whose annual income is less than RMB100,000, only 6.8% of them make decisions to study abroad. Families with an annual income of less than RMB200,000 have also become an important part of self-funded overseas payers, accounting for 52.7% of the total number of students who have made overseas study decisions. This shows that, on the one hand, although relatively low-income families make a small proportion of decision-making to study abroad, because of the large population base, students from lower-income families account for about half of all those who decide to study abroad. On the other hand, it also shows that although annual income seems difficult to support their children to study abroad, it does not prevent them from making decisions to support their children to study abroad. It means that they either acquire new ability to pay in addition to their annual income or choose relatively low-cost overseas education products. The sustained

development of China's economy and the substantial increase in per capita paid income constitute a strong push for self-supporting studying abroad. With the increase of household disposable income, the intensity of resistance caused by the cost of studying abroad has weakened. The number of foreign students enrolled in tertiary education programs worldwide has exploded over the past two decades. It rose from 2 million in 1999 to 5 million in 2016, at an average annual rate of 5.1% among OECD countries and 6.4 % among non-OECD countries (Education at a Glance 2018: OECD Indicators), shown as in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Growth in International or Foreign Enrolment in Tertiary Education Worldwide (1998-2016)

Source: Education at a Glance 2018: OECD Indicators.

The increase in foreign enrolment has been driven by a variety of domestic and external factors, both push (encouraging outward mobility) and pull factors (encouraging inward mobility) (UNESCO, 2013). The skills' needs increased knowledge-based and innovation-driven economies to spur demand for tertiary education worldwide, while local education capacities do not evolve fast enough to meet growing domestic demand. Rising wealth in emerging economies has further promoted students intending to enroll to higher learning institution to seek educational opportunities abroad. At the same time, economic factors, technological factors and cultural factors have contributed to the international mobility substantiality for a more affordable and less irreversible than the past (Education at a Glance 2018: OECD Indicators).

There are 1,260,000 China students studying abroad in 2015, accounting for about 25% of the total number of international students in the world, which one fourth of total international students are Chinese overseas students (Wang & Miao, 2016). As shown in Figure 2, in 2000-2016, the number of overseas students from China increased from 39,000 in 2000 to 544,500 in 2016, and the number of students studying abroad increased rapidly by an annual average of 15% (National Statistics Bureau of China, 2016). In 2018, the number of Chinese students studying abroad is 662,100, up 8.83% year-on-year (Ministry of Education of the People's Republic of China, 2019). In 1978-2016, the number of

students studying abroad has reached 4,586,600 people and China is still the largest source of foreign students in the world (Wang & Miao, 2017).

Figure 2: The Change in Number of Chinese Students Studying Abroad from 2000 to 2016

Source: Wang & Miao (2017).

The implementation of mobility programme emphasizing on student overall capabilities development in most higher learning Institutions in Malaysia has promoted the rapid expansion of the scale of higher education in Malaysia which has significantly improved the overall quality and level of higher education, and promoted the cooperation and communication between Malaysia universities and foreign universities. To a certain extent, the pull and competitiveness of Malaysia institutions of higher learning in the global international student education market were enhanced directly and indirectly, laying a solid foundation for attracting a large number of neighboring and distant state students and promoting the development of foreign students' Education in Malaysia. In 2013-2017, the number of Chinese students and foreign students enrolled by HEIs in Malaysia are shown in Table 1. Over the past five years, the number of foreign students enrolled by higher education institution in Malaysia has been in an increasing trend. The number and the proportion of Chinese students are increasing year by year. The number of Chinese students is the main foreign students in Malaysia.

Table 1: The Enrolment of Chinese Students and Foreign Students by HEIs in Malaysia, 2013-2017

Year	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
Enrolment of Chinese students	4,398	7,055	10,775	11,718	14,854
Enrolment of Foreign students	52,598	74,996	120,398	130,277	133,860
Proportion of Chinese students and foreign students	8.36%	9.41%	8.95%	8.99%	11.97%

Source: Ministry of Higher Education of Malaysia (2018).

According to Andrade (2006), foreign students have contributed to intercultural learning and have improved the understanding of diversity and global issues with the local countries. Hence, Malaysian students get more exposure on foreign culture as well as building understanding between each other. Furthermore, foreign students create international business opportunities and world trade connections, become diplomatic allies as well as promote foreign policy interests (Schneider, 2000 as cited in Andrade, 2006). In some cases, foreign students may consider staying in the country after graduation to fill up positions for which few nationals are qualified (Gray, 2003 as cited in Andrade, 2006). However, Malaysia has experienced a decline in the number of foreign students enrolling in Malaysian HEI such as Iran, Saudi Arabia, Maldives, Cambodia are among few others (Perangkaan Pendidikan Malaysia, 2013) Furthermore, there are neighboring countries such as Thailand and Singapore are aggressively promoting their own HEI (Migin, Falahat, Yajid & Khatibi, 2015). Other than that, based on the diagram above indicates the flow of foreign enrolment in Malaysian HEI is fluctuate over the past five years and it might become one of main obstacles for Malaysian HEI to accomplish the mission of achieve 200,000 foreign students in year 2020.

From the theoretical perspective, the “Push-Pull” theory has been widely applied in the field of education, including the phenomenon of studying abroad. The push-pull factor theory has become a widely accepted analytical framework to explain the reasons for international students’ mobility (Sun, 2017). Agarwal and Winkler (1985) tried to explore the factors that influence international students’ choice of studying in the United States. For the first time, Mc & Mary (1992) applied the “Push and Pull” theory to the field of education. Lawrence & Associates (1997) focused on the factors affecting the choice of destinations for Asian students. In view of the national political policy level, Philip (1998) used “Push-Pull” theory to study the impact of international student mobility. The international student mobility in developing countries can be attributed to the eight push forces of home countries and the seven pull forces of the host countries, shown as in Figure 3.

Source: Park (2009).

The development of “Push-Pull” theory in the field of education for decades, can be seen that it has emerged from simple to complex, recessive to dominant, generalization to concrete. The initial focus on the political level to the economic, cultural and social level; from the one-way “push” and “pull” of the home country and the host country to the two-way “push” and “pull”; from the national macro level to the individual micro level; from the external factors to the internal factors, comprehensive and systematic development, the theory developed systematically. At the same time, based on the research of critical “Push-Pull” theory scholars, the application in education field is improved day by day. The existing push and pull models of international students’ mobility mainly include: push and pull model of external factors, push and pull model of combining internal and external factors and push and pull model of interaction between internal and external factors (Li, 2015). As shown Figure 4, the new “Push-Pull” theory is put forward to combine the national macroscopic level with the individual microscopic level, which overcomes the problem of the separation of internal and external factors. At the same time, the two-way push and pull factors of country are also applied to the individual. In addition, the process factors of personal choice will also be reflected in the individual push-pull process. The new model also separates all the pull factors and all the push factors to clearly distinguish the internal relations between the two factors for horizontal and vertical comparison (Liu, 2013).

Figure 4: The “Push-Pull” Theory Model of International Student Mobility

Source: Liu (2013).

Many studies have shown that students’ personal factors influence their choice to study abroad. Students’ personal factors are usually summarized as objective conditions and subjective motivation (Liu, 2013; Li, 2015; Zhan, 2017, Quang & Ooi, 2017). Many

studies (Liu, 2013; Li, 2015; Zhan, 2017, Quang & Ooi, 2017) have also pointed out that students' objective conditions have an important impact on studying abroad, such as economy income, parents' education level, parents' occupation and so on. Sun (2017) conducted on the intention and influencing factors of high school students to study abroad in Suzhou, Jiangsu province of China. Using SPSS 18.0 to analyze the valid sample data of 504 students, it was found that nearly 50% of the students have the intention to go abroad for higher education. In terms of personal objective conditions, such factors as students' academic performance, English achievement, parents' education level, parents' occupation, family income level, students' expectations of studying abroad by their relatives and friends, and whether there are expatriates around them, have a significant impact on students' intention to choose cross-border higher education.

3. Research Methodology

According to the theory of "Push-Pull" and its application in the field of education, the pressure of Gaokao and employment, current situation of higher education are the external factors of China, which push Chinese high school students to study in Malaysia. Access and opportunities, characteristics of higher education are the external factors of Malaysia, which pull Chinese high school students to study in Malaysia. Family resources endowment and academic performance are the internal factors of Chinese students' objective conditions, which influence Chinese high school students to choose to study in Malaysia. Ability improvement, effect and expectation are the internal factors of Chinese students' subjective motivations, which influence Chinese high school students to choose to study in Malaysia. According to the Theory of Reason Action and the Theory of Planned Behavior and its application in the field of education, the intention refers to the tendency of Chinese high school students to make a decision and choose to study in Malaysia. Their perceptions and attitudes towards the influence of Chinese factors, Malaysian factors and their conditions and motivations, will affect their intention and choice to study in Malaysia.

The objective of this research is to verify the factors influencing Chinese high school students' intention to study in Malaysia from the perspective of Chinese factors and Malaysian factors. Thus, 5 main hypotheses were formulated for this study.

Hypothesis 1: There is a positive relationship between the push of China's factors and the students' intention to study abroad.

Hypothesis 2: There is a positive relationship between the Chinese students' objective conditions and the students' intention to study abroad.

Hypothesis 3: There is a positive relationship between the Chinese students' subjective motivations and the students' intention to study abroad.

Hypothesis 4: There is a positive relationship between the pull of Malaysia's factors and the students' intention to study abroad.

Hypothesis 5: There is a positive relationship between the Chinese students' intention and the choice to study at Malaysian HEIs.

The target population of this study is all the third-year high school students, who are in the urban area of four third-tier cities (Ganzhou, Jiujiang, Shangrao and Yichun) in Jiangxi province of China. As shown in Table 2, in 2018 the total number of students taking Gaokao in the urban areas of four third-tier cities is 20,389. The objective of this study is to examine factors that influence Chinese high school students' intention to choose to study abroad in Malaysia. Therefore, the unit of analysis is every third-year high school student, who is in the urban area of four third-tier cities (Ganzhou, Jiujiang, Shangrao and Yichun) in Jiangxi province of China. In this study, three probabilistic sampling designs are used to select sampling samples, namely, area sampling, proportional stratified sampling and simple random sampling. In this study, the unlimited probability sampling design or simple random sampling is utilized finally. This sampling design ensures that each element in the population has a known and equivalent possibility of being chosen as a subject. Simple random sampling is a fundamental sort of sampling, since it can be a part of other more complex sampling strategies. The standard of simple random sampling is that each object has the same probability of being picked. In this study, after the sample size of each city is determined, a simple random sampling can be used to select the research objects. Conceptually, simple random sampling is the simplest of the probability sampling techniques. It requires a complete sampling frame, which may not be accessible or practical to develop for substantial population. Even if a complete frame is available, approaches that are more efficient may be possible if other useful information is available about the units in the population. Points of interest are of this sampling designs incorporate free of classification error and least advance learning of the population other than the frame. Its simplicity also makes it relatively simple to interpret data collected in this way. Therefore, simple random sampling best suits circumstances where very little data is accessible about the population and data gathering can be adequately led on randomly distributed items, or where the cost of sampling is sufficiently little to make proficiency less important than simplicity. The sample frame is a list of all the elements in the population, and samples are also obtained from them. In this study, the sampling frame of population is all the third-year high school students, who are in the urban area of four third-tier cities in Jiangxi province. The sampling frame of each city is the third-year high school students, who are in the urban area of each city. The sampling frames of four cities (Ganzhou, Jiujiang, Shangrao and Yichun) constitute the sampling frame of population in this study. Table 3 illustrates as follows: Step one: regional sampling. The total number of urban high schools in four third-tier cities in Jiangxi province and the number of third-year high school students in each school are determined. The total number of students is the study population of this study. Step two: equally proportional sampling. First, the sample size is selected according to the study population. They were then divided equally among the four cities so that the sample size of each city could be determined. Finally, the sample size of each city was evenly distributed among all its high schools, so that the sample size of each high school could be determined. Step three: simple random

sampling. In each high school, every third-year student is randomly selected as survey an object.

Table 2: The Number of High School Students Applied the Gaokao in Urban Areas of the Four Cities, 2014-2018

City \ Year	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
Shangrao	4,658	4,778	4,958	4,686	4,804
Ganzhou	5,507	5,686	5,987	6,436	7,402
Yichun	3,447	3,575	3,886	3,892	4,136
Jiujiang	3,596	3,694	3,844	3,926	4,047
Total	17,208	17,733	18,675	18,940	20,389

Source: Education Bureaus of Four Cities (2018).

Table 3: Sampling Technique for This Study

Step	Process
Regional sampling	Sampling regions are selected from four cities.
Equally proportional sampling	Sampling size is distributed equally to four cities. Each city equally distributes sampling size to its every high school.
Simple random sampling	Every third-year student in each city's high school is selected randomly.

Source: Developed for this study (2018).

Table 4 outlined the result of the pilot study performed before the actual data collection. This was done in order to test the reliability of the items in each construct. On April 18, 2019, 60 questionnaires were distributed in Yichun Middle School. 48 completed pilot questionnaires were return, however only 31 were used for analysis.

Table 4: Result of Cronbach's Alpha for Pilot Study

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha
Push of China's Factors (PC)	0.879
Chinese Students' Objective Conditions (OC)	0.698
Chinese Students' Subjective Motivations (SM)	0.924
Pull of Malaysia's Factors (PM)	0.947
Students' Intention to Study Abroad (IM)	0.737
Chinese Students' Choice to Study at Malaysian HEIs (CM)	0.826

4. Research Findings and Discussion

The demographic study shows that the respondents, 235(54.9%) were males, 193(45.1%) were females in this study. The result of this study is that there are more males than females. This result of statistics is supported by Liu (2015) and sun (2017), that is, there are more males than females among Chinese overseas students. This study indicated that the number of students whose father has degree or diploma is the largest, reaching 184 (43.0%). 66 (15.4%) students stated their fathers either had a Master or PhD. The number of students whose father graduated from a high school or secondary specialized school

was 130 (30.4%). Only 48 (11.2%) students whose fathers graduated from middle school or below. As can be seen from the above data, among the high school students who are willing to study abroad, the majority of their fathers have received higher education, accounting for 58.4%. The number of students whose mother has degree or diploma is the largest, reaching 199 (46.5%). 19 (4.4%) students stated their mothers either had a Master or PhD. The number of students whose mother graduated from a high school or secondary specialized school was 139 (32.5%). 71 (16.6%) students whose mothers graduated from middle school or below. As can be seen from the above data, among the high school students who are willing to study abroad, the majority of their mothers have received higher education, accounting for 50.9%. In this study, 0.7 was adopted as the acceptable critical value. The results of questionnaire reliability analysis in this study are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Results of Reliability Analysis of Questionnaire Scale

Construct	Dimensions	Items	Cronbach's Alpha	
Push of China's Factors (PC)	Pressure of Gaokao and Employment (PoGE)	5	0.880	0.908
	Current Situation of HE (CSoHE)	5	0.893	
Chinese Students' Objective Conditions (OC)	Family Resources Endowment (FRE)	5	0.878	0.892
	Academic Performance (AP)	5	0.860	
Chinese Students' Subjective Motivations (SM)	Ability Improvement (AI)	5	0.873	0.806
	Effect and Expectation (EE)	5	0.880	
Pull of Malaysia's Factors (PM)	Access and Opportunities (AO)	5	0.897	0.912
	Characteristics of HE (CoHE)	5	0.904	
Students' Intention to Study Abroad (IM)		4	0.873	
Chinese Students' Choice to Study at Malaysian HEIs (CM)		4	0.853	

As can be seen from the above Table 5, Cronbach's Alpha coefficients of all variables in this study are all greater than 0.8, indicating that they all have strong reliability. After the statistical analysis of the reliability and validity of the questionnaire, this study had carried out confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) on the measurement models of six variables. The analysis results showed that the goodness-of-fit indices of the models all reach ideal values, indicating that the fitting degree of each measurement model and data is good. The modified structural equation model is shown as in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Modified Structural Equation Model

Table 6: Fitting index list of Modified Structural Equation Model

Fitness Index	Critical Value	Test Data	Fitting Judgment
X2		1184.756	
df		1061	
X2/df	1-3	1.117	Yes
SRMR	< 0.05	0.046	Yes
GFI	> 0.9	0.900	Yes
AGFI	> 0.9	0.889	Close to 0.9

NFI	>0.9	0.907	Yes
IFI	>0.9	0.989	Yes
TLI	>0.9	0.989	Yes
CFI	>0.9	0.989	Yes
RMSEA	<0.08	0.017	Yes

Table 6 shows that the fitting indices $GFI=0.900 \geq 0.9$, $AGFI=0.889$ close to 0.90, $NFI=0.907 > 0.90$, $CFI=0.989$, $RMSAE=0.017 < 0.05$, $SRMR=0.046 < 0.05$ in the modified structural equation model, all of which are ideal values, indicating that the modified structural equation model is acceptable. The corresponding path parameters are shown in Table 7, which provides a basis for later hypothesis testing.

Table 7: The Path Parameter List of Modified Structural Equation Model

Construct Path			S.E.	C.R. (T-value)	P	Standardized Estimate (Beta)
PC	----->	IM	0.057	6.550	***	0.363
OC	----->	IM	0.064	1.073	0.283	0.057
SM	----->	IM	0.084	5.584	***	0.313
PM	----->	IM	0.078	7.682	***	0.443
IM	----->	CM	0.060	10.538	***	0.577

Table 7 shows that the push of China's factors (PC), the Chinese students' subjective motivations (SM) and the pull of Malaysia's factors (PM) have a significant positive impact on the students' intention to study abroad (IM), and the students' intention to study abroad (IM) has a positive impact on the Chinese students' choice to study at Malaysian HEIs (CM). Therefore, the Bootstrapping is adapted to test whether the mediation effect was significant. The method adopted Bootstrap ML with 2000 repeated sampling to test the mediation effect results. Its 95% confidence interval contains 0, indicating no mediation, and if 0 is not included, indicating mediation, as shown in Table 8.

Table 8: The List of Bootstrap Mediation Effect

Mediation Path	Standardized Estimate	S.E.	Percentile Method (95%)		
			Lower Bounds	Upper Bounds	P
PC--IM--CM	$0.363 \times 0.577 = 0.209$	0.034	0.144	0.277	0.001
OC--IM--CM	$0.057 \times 0.577 = 0.033$	0.034	-0.031	0.105	0.311
SM--IM--CM	$0.313 \times 0.577 = 0.180$	0.033	0.115	0.246	0.001
PM--IM--CM	$0.443 \times 0.577 = 0.255$	0.033	0.191	0.319	0.001

Table 8 shows the four mediation paths and indicates whether the mediation effect exists, which provides a basis for later hypotheses testing.

4.1 Hypotheses Testing

The modified structural equation model in Figure 4 is used to test the relationships between the constructs based on the proposed hypotheses. Critical t-values for a two-

tailed test are 1.96 (significance level = 5 percent), 2.58 (significance level = 1 percent) and 3.24 (significance level = 0.1 percent). For this study, 5 percent significance level (t-value 1.96) was used as a statistical decision criterion. The result of each hypothesis will be tested and discussed below, total nine (9) hypotheses.

Hypothesis 1: There is a positive relationship between the push of China's factors (PC) and the students' intention to study abroad (IM).

Hypothesis 1 has been formulated to examine if there is positive relationship between the push of China's factors (PC) and the students' intention to study abroad (IM). According to the first line of path parameters in Table 7 (Beta =0.363, $P < 0.001$), the push of Chinese factors (PC) has a significant positive impact on the students' intention to study abroad (IM), which means that the push of Chinese factors (PC) will promote the students' intention to study abroad (IM). So, the hypothesis 1 is supported.

Hypothesis 2: There is a positive relationship between the Chinese students' objective conditions (OC) and the students' intention to study abroad (IM).

Hypothesis 2 has been formulated to examine if there is positive relationship between the Chinese students' objective conditions (OC) and the students' intention to study abroad (IM). According to the second line of path parameters in Table 7 (Beta =0.057, $P > 0.05$), the Chinese students' objective conditions (OC) has not a significant positive impact on the students' intention to study abroad (IM), which means that the Chinese students' objective conditions (OC) will not promote the students' intention to study abroad (IM). So, the hypothesis 2 is not supported.

Hypothesis 3: There is a positive relationship between the Chinese students' subjective motivations (SM) and the students' intention to study abroad (IM).

Hypothesis 3 has been formulated to examine if there is positive relationship between the Chinese students' subjective motivations (SM) and the students' intention to study abroad (IM). According to the third line of path parameters in Table 7 (Beta =0.313, $P < 0.001$), the Chinese students' subjective motivations (SM) has a significant positive impact on the Chinese students' intention to study abroad (IM), which means that the Chinese students' subjective motivations (SM) will promote the students' intention to study abroad (IM). So, the hypothesis 3 is supported.

Hypothesis 4: There is a positive relationship between the pull of Malaysia's factors (PM) and the students' intention to study abroad (IM).

Hypothesis 4 has been formulated to examine if there is positive relationship between the pull of Malaysia's factors (PM) and the students' intention to study abroad (IM). According to the fourth line of path parameters in Table 7 (Beta =0.443, $P < 0.001$), the pull of Malaysia's factors (PM) has a significant positive impact on the students' intention to study abroad (IM), which means that the pull of Malaysia's factors (PM) will promote the students' intention to study abroad (IM). So, the hypothesis 4 is supported.

Hypothesis 5: There is a positive relationship between the students' intention (IM) and choice to study at Malaysian HEIs (CM).

Hypothesis 5 has been formulated to examine if there is positive relationship between the students' intention (IM) and choice to study at Malaysian HEIs (CM). According to the fifth line of path parameters in Table 7 (Beta =0.557, $P < 0.001$), the students' intention (IM) has a significant positive impact on the choice to study at Malaysian HEIs (CM), which means that the students' intention (IM) will promote the choice to study at Malaysian HEIs (CM). So, the hypothesis 5 is supported.

Hypothesis 6: There is a positive relationship between the push of China's factors (PC) and the Chinese students' choice to study at Malaysian HEIs (CM) by the mediating effect of students' intention to study abroad (IM).

Hypothesis 6 is to test the mediating effect of students' intention to study abroad (IM) and there is a positive relationship between the push of China's factors (PC) and the Chinese students' choice to study at Malaysian HEIs (CM). According to the first line of bootstrap mediation effect Table 8, the standard estimate of the mediation path (PC--IM—CM) is 0.209, and the corresponding 95% confidence interval is [0.144, 0.277], which does not contain 0. It reaches significant level, and the mediation effect exists. That is, the students' intention to study abroad (IM) plays a mediating role in the influence of the push of China's factors (PC) on the Chinese students' choice to study at Malaysian HEIs (CM). So, the hypothesis 6 is supported.

Hypothesis 7: There is a positive relationship between the Chinese students' objective conditions (OC) and the Chinese students' choice to study at Malaysian HEIs (CM) by the mediating effect of students' intention to study abroad (IM).

Hypothesis 7 is to test the mediating effect of students' intention to study abroad (IM) and there is a positive relationship between the Chinese students' objective conditions (OC) and the Chinese students' choice to study at Malaysian HEIs (CM). According to the second line of bootstrap mediation effect Table 8, the standard estimate of the mediation path (OC--IM—CM) is 0.033, and the corresponding 95% confidence interval is [-0.031, 0.105], which contains 0. It does not reach significant level, and the mediation effect does not exist. That is, the students' intention to study abroad (IM) does not play a mediating role in the influence of the Chinese students' objective conditions (OC) on the Chinese students' choice to study at Malaysian HEIs (CM). So, the hypothesis 7 is not supported.

Hypothesis 8: There is a positive relationship between the Chinese students' subjective motivations (SM) and the Chinese students' choice to study at Malaysian HEIs (CM) by the mediating effect of students' intention to study abroad (IM).

Hypothesis 8 is to test the mediating effect of students' intention to study abroad (IM) and there is a positive relationship between the Chinese students' subjective motivations (SM) and the Chinese students' choice to study at Malaysian HEIs (CM).

According to the third line of bootstrap mediation effect Table 8, the standard estimate of the mediation path (SM--IM—CM) is 0.180, and the corresponding 95% confidence interval is [0.115, 0.246], which does not contain 0. It reaches significant level, and the mediation effect exists. That is, the students' intention to study abroad (IM) plays a mediating role in the influence of the Chinese students' subjective motivations (SM) on the Chinese students' choice to study at Malaysian HEIs (CM). So, the hypothesis 8 is supported.

Hypothesis 9: There is a positive relationship between the pull of Malaysia's factors (PM) and the Chinese students' choice to study at Malaysian HEIs (CM) by the mediating effect of students' intention to study abroad (IM).

Hypothesis 9 is to test the mediating effect of students' intention to study abroad (IM) and there is a positive relationship between the pull of Malaysia's factors (PM) and the Chinese students' choice to study at Malaysian HEIs (CM). According to the fourth line of bootstrap mediation effect Table 8, the standard estimate of the mediation path (PM--IM—CM) is 0.255, and the corresponding 95% confidence interval is [0.191, 0.319], which does not contain 0. It reaches significant level, and the mediation effect exists. That is, the students' intention to study abroad (IM) plays a mediating role in the influence of the pull of Malaysia's factors (PM) on the Chinese students' choice to study at Malaysian HEIs (CM). So, the hypothesis 9 is supported.

After nine (9) hypotheses were tested, the comprehensive results are shown in Table 9.

Table 9: The Result of Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis	Conclusion
H1: PC has a positive relationship with IM	Supported
H2: OC has a positive relationship with IM	Not Supported
H3: SM has a positive relationship with IM	Supported
H4: PM has a positive relationship with IM	Supported
H5: IM has a positive relationship with CM	Supported
H6: IM plays a mediating role in the influence of PC on CM	Supported
H7: IM plays a mediating role in the influence of OC on CM	Not Supported
H8: IM plays a mediating role in the influence of SM on CM	Supported
H9: IM plays a mediating role in the influence of PM on CM	Supported

5. Conclusion

This research has contributed to the theoretical implications. Notably, this study improves the current written literature on influential factors towards intention of student enrolment in HEI. The factors being examined are student belief, social influence and brand equity. According to Shaw (2005) stated that previous studies have offer some examples, recommendations and considerations for institutions in structuring and carrying out their own research studies on the educational benefits of diversity. Therefore, the finding from this study can help researchers to have a clear insight and

greater understanding of foreign students' enrolment of HEI in Malaysia in future by referring this research study. Next, the findings of this study provide reference for students, academician or researchers who plan to study and research in this field as there is less established research done towards foreign students' enrolment of HEI in Malaysia. Last but not least, Universities build a recognizable brand by creating a memorable logo. It should represent the universities have positively image and able to convey a message to people, and it should be easy for people to make a connection between the brand and the education that attempts to be offer. Besides, it can be used as a guideline for those students looking for further study after finished the secondary school life.

This study has several limitations. Firstly, foreign students were the only specific age of group (majority in the age group of 19-25) that centralized in this study. Hence, the result of this research will not be accurate if the target respondent is altered to other age groups like the age from 17 to 18. Thus, future researchers are advisable to ensure target respondents of questionnaire survey are distributed fairly based on the region and age group ratio to produce a result with higher generalizability and representative for all foreign students.

Although the questionnaire for this study has been enhanced and corrected after the conduct of pilot study, but there are chances that some respondent might answer the questionnaire without proper consideration because of time constraints. Some of respondents might also giving imprecise respond during the survey as they think and believe that some of the information acquired may infringe their privacy or language barrier among the respondent. These circumstances will influence the researchers from receiving actual and accurate information related to this research.

Researchers are recommended to expand the study to a wider geographical area or different age groups for better generalization in the forthcoming research. Instead of just a single university, future research can be done by including other universities in Malaysia as there are different regions and age group foreign students so they might have different thoughts towards enrolment of HEIs in Malaysia. Besides that, researchers are also recommended to ensure that target respondents for questionnaire survey are distributed fairly based on the region and age group ratio to acquire result with greater generalizability and representative for all foreign students.

Nevertheless, there are some recommendations to overcome the problem of accuracy and trustable of the data obtain through the questionnaire that leads by the inappropriate answer provided by the respondents due to their language barrier or other factors. Firstly, before distribute the questionnaire to the respondents, the researcher have to give a precise description about the purpose of conducting this questionnaire to let the respondent to felt this questionnaire is safe and the privacy is protected when they are answering the questionnaire. Moreover, the researchers can assist the respondents to answer the questionnaire if they meet any problem when the times, they submit their questionnaire back to the researcher.

In a conclusion, this study had achieved the research objective in determining the determinants of foreign student enrolment in Malaysia HEIs. Scale measurement with

internal scale and inferential analysis has conducted to examine the relationship between independent variables and dependent variables. Last but not least, this finding indicates that all the independent variables have a significant relationship towards foreign student enrolment. However, the social influence does not bring a huge effect towards the foreign student enrolments in Malaysia because the beta value is the lowest as compared to the other 2 independent variables.

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